

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MODERN ASPECTS OF GUARANTEEING THE STABILITY OF CONTRACTS IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

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Abstract

In modern conditions, compared to the earlier periods, the attitude of the parties to the contract during the preparation of contracts in international business has changed significantly. An international business contract is the main driver of agreement between the business participants. It significantly determines the successful state of business. The purpose of the contract is to harmonize international business relations. Along with the development of blockchain technology and digital communication systems at the modern stage, the interest in smart contract as the most effective tool of this technology is growing. It is through the smart contract that the business can receive the benefits resulted from the development of information technology.

Keywords: Business contracts, legal systems, human factor, blockchain system, smart contract

The main text

Among the many factors affecting international business, one of the important and "influential" factors is the main legislative and legal acts, laws of both own and host countries. Every step from the company's initial activity to the international market is regulated and the main goal is reached based on them. This factor is equally crucial for all countries - whether it is a producer or a consumer.

In general, the legal systems of countries differ due to their cultural, historical or political background. There are three types of legal systems: general, civil and religious. It is these three main signs that create a mechanism for regulating international relations all over the world, including in the field of international business.

General law is based on the collective experience of making decisions accumulated throughout the history of the country on separate judicial activities. Laws governing the conduct of business are characterized by their specificity, which creates a problem for misinformed entrepreneurs. Religious law is based on officially established rules of faith and religion. Theocracy is a management form that regulates civil and criminal behavior of citizens. It happens that sometimes religious law can cause significant problems in the company's activities.

For example: according to the Muslim Koran, charging interest on a loan is considered an unfair exploitation of the poor. Therefore, financial organizations are forced to develop and implement alternative options. Systems based on religious law are also characterized by other features. For example, lack of appropriate court procedures and appeal filing procedures, etc. All this depends on the religious traditions of the country.

In modern conditions, compared to the earlier periods, the attitude of the parties to the contract during the preparation of contracts in international business

has changed significantly. In particular, paying attention to and accounting for such details became equally important, which were previously, on the contrary, neglected. In this way, contractors emphasize mutual respect for partners, which may be related to the traditions, religion, and national values of the partner country. Taking into account the partner's interests and making certain concessions when making decisions is accepted in international business. Obviously, this does not mean putting one's own interests in the background and withdrawing one's positions as a result of concessions. We are talking about newly formed and established signs of mutual respect and collegiality. In such a case, both sides of the contract remain winners. A reliable and solid relationship is formed. Obviously, both parties to the contract should equally try and aim to acquire a reliable and long-term partner, who in return is ready to take into account the same reverse actions.

At the same time, we cannot ignore the fact that there are a number of issues and strictly controlled regulations, which must be observed and fulfilled, and no changes can be made there by the parties. In particular, international law plays an important role in international business, it regulates relations between states. By law, one country can force another to agree to unacceptable policy changes, using trade restrictions and sanctions. Sanctions can be: quota, refusal of new credits, restriction of access to high-tech products, boycott of the country's goods, etc. An international business contract is a document necessary to achieve business goals, which protects intellectual property, trade secrets and reduces risk in the international market. It can be said that an international business contract is the main driver of agreement between business participants. It significantly determines the successful state of business. The purpose of the contract is to harmonize international business relations.

In order to avoid business failure, it is necessary that all terms of the contract to be properly observed and drafted by lawyers. Depending on the international

nature of the contract, it may be defined in different ways. International business contracts represent an important connection between two or more states and impose certain obligations on all parties to each other. The issues of concluding and canceling the contract, as well as its validity, are legally regulated by international law, the positions of the parties are clearly reflected in it.

The role of statistical data in contracts and international business is important. In general, statistics and statistical data help consumers, governments, investors and other business stakeholders to make better decisions and develop the future. Consumers need statistics to know when and where to buy the goods or services they need and want. On the other hand, businesses actively use statistical information to make full-fledged decisions: what, where, how much to produce. Statistical information allows for forecasting future periods, how much production can be expanded or vice versa, orders the time of market reduction and displacement, etc.

The government of any country makes important decisions and changes based on statistical information, along with business. From which areas to receive stable and guaranteed payments, how and in what way to attract new and additional resources, as well as where, in what amount and priority to spend the existing revenues, etc.

The modern statistical system, with its full-fledged and universally understandable information, provides considerable assistance to international business partners in business proposals and offers, in the preparation of international contracts, in obtaining any necessary information about each other. It is for this purpose that the national accounts system, monetary and financial statistics, balance of payments statistics and international investment situation, government finance statistics were developed by the specialists of the statistical service of international organizations. However, at every stage of human development, new economic challenges arise that require statistical study and analysis. Along with the mentioned indicators, a number of international regulatory legal acts, contracts play an important role in the signing of international business contracts: The Charter of the United Nations, the Convention on Climate Change, the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants.

International contract is the main source of international law. The importance of international law is great in international business. Therefore, the role of the contract is also clear. The purpose of an international business contract is to regulate important issues between states or organizations.

Due to the fact that the contract is signed between the parties, in the process of doing business, arise important issues, the parties' positions, requirements, goals, which must be protected and inviolable in the future.

Contract is a very important factor in the regulation of international business. Due to the fact that business is associated with constant risk, many changes and even disagreements between parties, it is necessary to

have a document that will legally guarantee the satisfaction of all the requirements, conditions, positions, and wishes of business producers.

If a business with an international level does not have a contract between the parties, the possibility of its failure will increase and the level of risks will increase. Also, when the company is in the international market and has a similar type of responsibility, it is necessary to verify each of its actions in the form of a contract to avoid unpleasant consequences in the future. A contract is a guarantee that every obligation that exists between the parties is reliable. Nowadays, contractual business relationships, both domestically and internationally, have grown considerably. Due to the fact that everything in the world is constantly changing, people are constantly looking for stability or "subject" that will guarantee stability. It is the contract that guarantees stability in the regulation of international business

Thus, a stable and successful international business regulation is impossible without a contract, the legal norms that it possesses make it unique in this respect, because only a contract can fulfill the regulation of business legally in the long term and its future in a risky world.

Today, quite a lot is changing in terms of international contracts and the conclusion of contracts in general, and most importantly, increasing the stability and reliability of contracts. We would like to express our modest opinion regarding the current news

With the development of blockchain technologies and digital communication systems at the modern stage, the interest in smart contract as the most effective tool of the said technology is growing. It is through the smart contract that the business can receive the benefits that result from the development of information technology.

Talking about smart contract became relevant after the appearance of blockchain and cryptocurrency in the Internet space. Blockchain and smart contract are considered as a legally recognized method of data storage, provided that they do will not contradict with existing rules and laws. An electronic signature carried out in the blockchain system is interpreted as having legal force. If the parties have chosen the blockchain as their data storage location, then the data from such a source is considered legally valid. A contract cannot be deprived of legal force or enforcement on the grounds that an electronic signature was used when concluding the contract and the terms are given in the form of a smart contract.

Electronic signature in the blockchain system is recognized by law. A signature and contract protected by blockchain technology is considered electronic.

At the level of international business, harmonization and standardization of common standards, norms and characteristics around smart contracts are underway under the auspices of blockchain technology. An international technical committee - ISO/TC307: «Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies» has been created under the leadership of the International Organization for Standardization, which works on specific standards, in specific registries, including smart contracts. The committee is faced with the task of

whether a smart contract will be able to simplify or replace legal mechanisms.

The success of the smart contract and the efficiency of business relationship regulation mostly depend on the synchronous development of technical and legal progress. Along with the development of digital technologies, legislative support will significantly increase the scale of smart contracts, allowing them to be widely used in today's rather "accelerated" world pulse. Today, smart contracts can be used in both commercial and financial transactions, as well as social transactions: inheritance, labor and insurance relations. In Georgia, since 2017, the law "On Electronic Documents and Electronic Trust Services" is in force. It is desirable to adopt such a legislative act as the law "On Digital Economy". This would enable the deployment and operation of smart contracts. Transactions in a number of business areas or legal matters of various legal significance and types would automatically be regulated.

Today, a very common and widely known type of smart contract is blockchain. It is a database that is automatically managed, it does not have a single center. Information is stored and updated simultaneously, in different devices. Blockchain securely stores information, at the same time, also providing key information to the smart contract. Blockchain increases reliability in the sense that there is a greater trust factor between the parties due to the existence of a uniform document. Several persons are guaranteed with unchanged information and most importantly, technical attack is excluded.

There are two types of existing blockchain platforms: public and private (blockchain consortia). Their use depends on the type of projects. In particular, blockchain is used where it is necessary to eliminate the distrust factor (there is distrust between partners...), or it is impossible to use a centralized platform.

Smart contracts were soon "accepted" and approved, because they are characterized by the main features that characterize today's world relations, first of all, quickness and less time spending. Second and important - the main value of the contract is to make the obligation self-fulfilling, it no longer depends on or minimizes the risks, relieves the participants of the contract and leaves them with the least chance of not fulfilling their obligations. To hide important facts and to violate the deadlines. Because the rights of the parties are so strictly limited, the risks are less. As a result, the

business receives stable income, better management of receivables and payables, there are fewer commercial and financial disputes.

In fact, a smart contract is similar to a physical contract, the difference is that it is digital, is a computer program, and is stored in the blockchain system. It is called the smart contract software model. It establishes the rules of business transactions, negotiations, automatically confirms the terms of performance and enforcement.

So, smart contracts are considered as a guarantee of the stability of contracts in international business. The competitive environment of the modern market economy does not allow for the luxury of time. The Covid-19 pandemic also clearly showed us that negotiation and agreement can be done without meetings and direct connections, and moreover, it is associated with lower costs. It is important technologies to be modern and in good order.

The factor of human and human relations gradually moves to the background. We are getting used to the standards and framework of business relationships that will only be offered by the programs. Over time, the features that differentiate countries and states, which we talked about at the beginning of the article, will no longer be remembered. No one will have the obligation to take into account the interests of the partner... We will all be organized and adjusted to the same standards in the same digital world.

And will this be a modern guarantor of the stability of contracts in international business!?

In an automatically managed database created by a person, where information is stored and updated simultaneously, in different devices, blockchain increases reliability in the sense that there is a greater trust factor between the parties due to the existence of a uniform document and it can be confidently claimed that this is a guarantee of reliability?!

The current situation is a time factor. Human relations are indispensable even at the peak of technological progress. Blockchain trustworthiness and smart contracts will only partially replace human relationships.

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